

Description of appressoria produced by *S. oryzae* isolates.

Isolate	Color of appressoria	Range in the dimensions of appressoria (mm) ^a		Lobes/appressorium (no.) ^a
		Length	Width	
Hyderabad (Andhra Pradesh)	Dark brown	13-29	7-23	8
Kapurthala (Punjab)	Dark brown	12-28	10-23	8
Titabar (Assam)	Brown	14-30	11-25	6
Kapurthala (Punjab)	Dark brown	12-28	10-23	8
Coimbatore (Tamil Nadu)	Brown	14-31	13-29	5
Madurai (Tamil Nadu)	Light brown	11-29	9-24	10
Kaul (Haryana)	Light brown	13-26	9-25	9
Lakhimpur (Uttar Pradesh) (UP)	Dark brown	15-33	12-29	8
Sitapur (UP)	Light brown	14-28	10-24	7
Pantnagar (UP)	Light brown	12-28	10-24	7
Pantnagar (UP)	Dark brown	13-29	11-26	8
Pantnagar (UP)	Dark brown	14-29	11-26	6
Pantnagar (UP)	Dark brown	15-30	12-29	9
Pantnagar (UP)	Light brown	15-32	11-28	8
Pantnagar (UP)	Light brown	14-30	9-26	7
Pantnagar (UP)	Light brown	12-30	8-26	7

^aAv of 50 appressoria

contact with the host surface (Fig. c). All the isolates produced lobate, multicellular appressoria (Fig. d) that varied in color, size, and number of lobes/appressorium (Table 1).

The appressoria were observed to form infection pegs which penetrated directly through the cuticle into the epidermal cell and produced subepidermal mycelia (Fig. e). In some cases, an infection cushion did not form; hyphae penetrated directly through the host surface (Fig. f) and then ramified in parenchymatous tissues. As the hyphae thickened and branched, the host cell disintegrated and the host tissue became damaged extensively (Fig. g). ■

Managing ufra disease in deepwater rice (DWR) in Assam, India

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Ufra disease, caused by *Ditylenchus angustus*, is a major biotic constraint in DWR in Assam. We compared the effects of several management practices on disease severity under field conditions in a preidentified ufra-infected area. Experiments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Seeds of popular (but highly ufra-susceptible) local DWR variety

Rangabao were sown at 15-d intervals on 20 Mar, 4 Apr, 19 Apr, and 4 May in 1990 and 1991 wet seasons. Disease severity was recorded as percentage of infected tillers/hill (Table 1).

In a separate experiment, we compared the effects of soaking seeds and/or spraying plants with pesticides hostathion and monocrotophos, and growing resistant variety Rayada 16-06

and early-maturing variety Padmapani on disease severity.

The late-sown (4 May) crop suffered the lowest disease severity compared with early- and normally sown crops (Table 1). Padmapani completely escaped from the disease. Rayada 16-06 had the lowest disease severity compared with other treatments (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Effect of resistant and early-maturing varieties and pesticide treatments on ufra disease severity in DWR. Assam, India, 1990 and 1991 wet seasons.

Treatment	Disease severity ^a (% infected tillers/hill)		
Resistant variety (Rayada 16-06)	10.7	(19.6) ^b	b
Early-maturing variety (Padmapani)	0	(4.1)	a
Soaking seeds with hostathion 0.2% for 6 h	38.5	(38.6)	d
Soaking seeds with monocrotophos 0.2% for 6 h	58.5	(50.2)	ef
Spraying with hostathion 0.2% (45 and 80 DAS) ^c	49.0	(44.7)	de
Spraying with monocrotophos 0.2% (45 and 80 DAS)	47.9	(44.1)	de
Soaking seeds + spraying with hostathion 0.2%	13.9	(22.3)	b
Soaking seeds + spraying with monocrotophos 0.2%	25.1	(30.4)	c
Control	65.0	(54.0)	f
LSD (0.05)		6.7	

^aIn a column, mean values with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bFigures in parentheses are angular transformed values. ^cDAS = d after sowing.

Table 1. Effect of sowing date on ufra disease severity in DWR. Assam, India, 1990 and 1991 wet seasons.

Sowing date	Disease severity (% infected tillers/hill)	
20 Mar	91.7	(73.3) ^a
4 Apr	82.0	(64.9)
19 Apr	33.6	(35.4)
4 May	22.0	(8.0)
LSD (0.05)		(4.8)

^aFigures in parentheses are angular transformed values.